

ISSN 2349-1027

International Registered & Recognized Research Journal Related to Higher Education for All Subjects
INDO WESTERN RESEARCHERS

REFEREED & PEER REVIEWED RESEARCH JOURNAL

Vol. II, Issue : V
Year- III, Bi-Annual (Half Yearly)
(Aug. 2015 To Jan. 2016)

Editorial Office :
'Gyandev-Parvati',
R-9/139/6-A-1,
Near Vishal School,
LIC Colony,
Pragati Nagar, Latur
Dist. Latur - 413531.
(Maharashtra), India.

EDITOR IN CHIEF

Dr. Ambuja Malkhedkar
Gulbarga, Dist. Gulbarga
(Karnataka)

EXECUTIVE EDITORS

Dr. Nita Bhosale
Dept. of Hindi,
Govt. Ist Grade College,
Kamlapur, Dist. Gulbarga (Karnataka)

Dr. Bataji G. Kamble
Head, Dept. of Economics,
Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar College,
Latur, Dist. Latur (M.S.)

DEPUTY EDITOR

Dr. Gururaj V. Menkudale
Dept. of Dairy Science,
Mahatma Basweshwar College,
Latur, Dist. Latur (M.S.)

Dr. Balaji D. Ingale
Principal
Sharadchandra Mahavidyalaya,
Naigaon, Dist. Nanded (M.S.)

Website
www.irasg.com

CO - EDITOR

Dr. Sanjivani B. Wadekar
Dept. of Dairy Science,
Sharadchandra Mahavidyalaya,
Naigaon, Dist. Nanded (M.S.)

Sandipan K. Gayake
Dept. of Sociology,
Vasant Mahavidyalaya,
Kaj, Dist. Beed (M.S.)

Contact : - 02382 - 241913
09423346913 / 09637935252
09503814000 / 07276301000

MEMBER OF EDITORIAL BOARD

E-mail :
visiongroup1994@gmail.com
interlinkresearch@rediffmail.com
mbkamble2010@gmail.com

Dr. Mohammad T. Rahaman
Dept. of Biomedical Science,
International Islamic University,
Mahkota (Malaysia)

Dr. Eknath J. Helge
Head, Dept. of Commerce,
Jijamata Mahavidyalaya,
Buldhana, Dist. Buldhana (M.S.)

Dr. Satyen Kumar P. Sitapara
Principal
Commerce & BBA College,
Amreli, Dist. Amreli (Gujrat)

Dr. Aitabaksha Jamadar
Head, Dept. of Hindi,
B. K. D. College,
Chakur, Dist. Latur (M.S.)

Dr. Y. K. Thombare
Principal
N. S. S. College,
Dodamarg, Dist. S. Durg (M. S.)

Dr. Sivappa Rasapali
Dept. of Chemistry & Biochemistry,
UMASS, Westport Road,
Dartmouth, MA (U.S.A.)

Dr. Sarjerao R. Shinde
Principal
B. K. D. College,
Chakur, Dist. Latur (M.S.)

Dr. Arun Kumbhar
Head, Dept. of Economics,
Arts & Commerce College,
Near, Dist. Kolhapur (M.S.)

Dr. Saktharam V. Kakade
Dept. of Zoology,
Vasant Mahavidyalaya,
Kaj, Dist. Beed (M.S.)

Dr. Vinod Veer
Head, Dept. of Geography,
Kishan Veer College,
Wai, Dist. Satara (M.S.)

Published by :
Indo Asian Publication,
Latur, Dist. Latur - 413531 (M.S.) India

Price : ₹ 200/-

**THE DEPLETION OF GROUNDWATER LEVEL IN SOLAPUR DISTRICT
: A GEOGRAPHICAL ANALYSIS****Dr. N. G. Mali***Head, Dept. of Geography,
Mahatma Basवेश्वर College,
Latur, Dist. Latur***Dr. V. C. Damde***Dept. of Geography,
DBF Dayanand College,
Solapur, Dist. Solapur***D. N. Ligade***Dept. of Geography,
Walchand College,
Solapur, Dist. Solapur***ABSTRACT**

The prime objective of this research is to study and examine the groundwater decline in Solapur district. Solapur district is one of the most useful district in western Maharashtra for agricultural development, which located rain shadow zone. Over-exploitation of groundwater resources is the major problem leading to groundwater depletion in Solapur district. Groundwater depletion has more than doubled during the last decades, primarily due to increase in water demand. In recent decades there have been frequent conflicts between groundwater and over-exploitation of ground water resource, which the major problem leading to groundwater resources and environmentally hazards activity. In last decades, rapid population growth coupled with agricultural expansion has significantly increased demand on ground resources. Large increase in water demand with little recharge have strained groundwater resources resulting in declines in water level and deterioration of groundwater quality in the major parts of this region. It's worth mentioning the paramount cause of sharp drop in the groundwater table in recent years is conclusively attributed to pumping out of well water which confirmedly exceeds the level of the natural recharge. As a result, the average water level has dropped 10 meter during the years from 2008 to 2013, but in 2014 it's decline 1.57 meter as compare average of 2008 to 2013.

Keywords: Aquifer, water level decline, gestation, paucity

Introduction:

Groundwater is a vital natural resource. It is estimated that approximately one third of the world's population use groundwater for drinking. In the study area, the extensive agricultural activities and urbanization resulted in the contamination of the aquifer in recent years. Ground water plays a crucial role in the country in increasing food and agricultural production, providing drinking water and facilitating industrial development. Ground water meets nearly 55% of irrigation, 85% of rural and 50% urban and industrial water needs. The use of ground water in the agriculture sector has expanded rapidly because of the short gestation lags with which it can be developed, control over irrigation that it provides, free or subsidized availability of power in some states and paucity of surface irrigation. Ground water levels in various parts of India are declining as the country could not adequately recharge aquifers in deficit areas where it has been used for irrigation, industries and drinking water needs of the growing population over the years. The Central Ground Water Board (CGWB) has told the ministry of water resources that around 56% of the wells, which are analyzed to keep a tab on ground water level, showed decline in its level in 2013 as compared to the average of preceding 10 years (2003-12) period.

Solapur is one of the most progressive and the leading district in the Maharashtra with reference to groundwater based irrigation development and water supply. Out of a total area of 14845 sq. km., 70.48 percent is under cultivation, 17.44 per cent of the cultivated area is under irrigation of which more than 45 percent is based on groundwater, utilizing dugwells and borewells.

Study Region:

Solapur district has been selected as per study which is in the western Maharashtra. The district of Solapur lies entirely in Bhima-Sina river basin of Maharashtra state. The Solapur district bounded by 17010' N to 18032' N latitudes and 74010' E to 76015' E longitudes. The Solapur district is spread over 14,845 sq.km. with 11 talukas, Solapur occupies 4.83% area and contains 3.84% population of Maharashtra state. Average rainfall of the district is less than 750 mm. As per 2011 census the total population accounts 43,155,227 roughly equal to the nation of Maldiva of the US state of Kentucky. This gives it a ranking of 43 rd in India (out of total 640).

Map No.1 Location Map of Solapur District

Objectives:

To formulate a management strategy, a model was set of following objectives-

1. To analyses the spatial distribution of ground water depletion in study region.
2. To find out the causes of ground water depletion level.

Data collection and Methodology:

The entire study is based on secondary data as like various published reports, Socio-Economic Review of Solapur district, and daily news papers from 2008 to 2014. The trend of ground water depletion is calculated and represented using the choropleth cartographic method.

Current status of groundwater level in Solapur district:

The underline basalt on disintegration and decomposition brought varieties agencies had yielded three kinds of soils viz. Deep soil (18.2%), medium deep (13.9%) and shallow soils (67.8%). There are 168 observation wells in Solapur district. This helps to detect the increasing and decreasing trend of ground water level in this district. There are some regions in

Solapur district where the decreasing water level indicate the person to sustainable use of water is now essential.

Fig No. 1 Comparison of SWL of Last Six year average and 2014

In Solapur district the distribution of ground water depletion level categorized in three types, which are given below.

1. Low depletion of ground water level (Below 1m):

The following map shows that there are three tahsils in Solapur district which indicates the low depletion of ground water level. Akkalkot (0.60m), South Solapur (0.82) and Sangola (0.94) are the tahsils where the depletion ground water level is below 1m. South Solapur tahsil's some part occupied by plat region, where the ground water and the river is main source of water. The extreme eastern parts of Akkalkot taluka is a broken hill ground with a number of north-south spurs; this ground forms a tertiary watershed and flat topped. These hills are covered with loose boulders and plentiful nodules and kankar. So these tahsil has low depletion of ground water level which is below 1 meter.

2. Medium depletion of ground water level (Between 1 to 1.5m):

In this section there are four tahsils where the depletion of ground water level is between 1 to 1.5 m. Mangalwedha (1.03), Karmala (1.17m), Malshiras (1.19m) and North Solapur (1.45m) are tahsils of which tahsils depletion level is between 1 to 1.5 m. Mangalwedha tahsil is popular for black soil where high jawar is main crops which depend on monsoon. Karmala thasil rises to a bare 600 meters above mean sea level and about 50 to 60 meters above the level of the adjoining valley floor. A broken hill range forming a low tableland and a

water-shed between the drainages of the Bhima and the Sina runs in a northwesterly-southeasterly direction. Malshiras plain at an elevation of about 550 metres which are drained both to the north and the east by the tributaries of the Nira and Bhima rivers and North Solapur is the small tahsil in Solapur district but the use of ground water is very high due to the high population concentrated in the Solapur City.

Map No.2 Solapur District Tahsilwise Ground water depletion level

**SOLAPUR DISTRICT
Ground Water Depletion Level**

3. Medium depletion of ground water level (Above 1 to 1.5m):

Barshi (2.19m), Pandharpur (2.22m) and Madha (2.65m) are the tahsils where the proportion of groundwater depletion level very high due to excessive use of water for not only agriculture but also daily use. In the eastern and northern parts of Barshi taluka, Balaghat hills outcrop and rise to the elevations of over 600 metres. So after the heavy rainfall the water do

not prevent. Pandharpur tahsil lies near the Bhima River where excessive water used for agriculture. And Madha tashils's some part is hills where the water do not use agriculture. So these tahsils has high depletion of ground water level in solapur district.

Conclusion:

Groundwater is the unique source of water for all purposes in the Solapur district. Due to population and agricultural growth, the demand for water has increased significantly. Therefore, groundwater sources can't meet the demand. The aquifer of the plain is already being over-exploited, resulting a fall in groundwater level. The results show that groundwater in the major portions of the study area are characterised by high concentrations of major cations and anions due to the continuous decline of groundwater level. Following are the main causes and strategies for depletion of ground water level in Solapur district.

1. Poor monsoon due to climate change has further aggravated the groundwater situation since the latter heavily depends on rains. Poor rainfall compels the farmers to dig further down for groundwater to irrigate the field. This results in pushing the tables deeper down in the Solapur district.
2. The bursting population is a reason for insufficient water per head. While it has been estimated that the amount of usable water.
3. Excess extraction by farmers in Solapur district has led to the dwindling groundwater supplies. This is so because access to groundwater is free and anyone has a right to pump water from their own land.
4. However, the over-exploitation of groundwater is an environmental hazard which causes the salinity of groundwater and makes it unsuitable for the irrigation of fertile lands as well as for the drinking purposes in the region.
5. Depleting ground water level may be a real worry if one looks at the future demand of water in Solapur district. So peoples plays vital role in sustainable use water resources.
6. It is necessary to improve the allocation of groundwater resources for agricultural and domestic.
7. Improving the irrigation efficiency we can decrease the depletion of ground water level in Solapur district.

References :-

1. Bhagyashri C. Maggirwarl and Bhavana N. Umrikar " Influence of various factors on the fluctuation of groundwater level in hard rock terrain and its importance in the assessment of groundwater."
2. Central Ground Water Board (CGWB). 1995. Groundwater resources of India. Faridabad, India, Central Groundwater Board, Ministry of Water Resources, Government of India.
3. Dr.N.G.Mali, Dr.V.C.Dande, Shri.D.N.Ligade "A strategy for controlling groundwater depletion in the Maharashtra" Aayushi International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, Vol.I, Issue.III, Aug 2014.
4. Frederick, K.D. (1993) Balancing Water Demands with Supplies: The Role of Management in a World of Increasing Scarcity, World Bank Technical Paper 189 (Washington, DC, World Bank).
5. Groundwater Resources Estimation Committee (1997) "Groundwater resources estimation methodology - 1997" . Ministry of Water Resources, Government of India., pp. 1-107.
6. Groundwater Surveys and Development Agency (1990) Maharashtra State, India: Proceedings of the National Seminar on Rainwater Harvesting, Pune, India. Isohyte map printed on back cover page.
7. Groundwater Surveys and Development Agency (2004) "Estimation of Groundwater Resources in Maharashtra" (as per GEC 1997), Groundwater Surveys and Development Agency, GoM.
8. Indian Meteorological Department (1972) Climate of Maharashtra., p. 114.
9. McGuire, V. L. (2003), Water level changes in the High Plains Aquifer, pre-development to 2001, 1999-2000, and 2000-2001, USGS Fact Sheet 078-03, U.S. Geol. Surv., Denver, Colo.
10. Radhakrishna BP (1971) Problems confronting the occurrence of groundwater in hard rocks., In: Groundwater Potential in Hard Rock Areas in India., Geol. Soc. Ind. Publ., pp. 27-44.
11. Shah, T. 1993. Groundwater markets and irrigation development: political economy and practical policy. Mumbai, India, Oxford University Press.
12. Central Ground water Board- Ground water scenario of India, 2010
dhanesh.ligade@gmail.com